

The health-income gap: To what extent does income explain health disparities in people with spinal cord injury?

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Dedication

This work is dedicated to my family, who has been a fundamental pillar in this whole process despite being far away.

Years ago my grandfather told me, Anita, study with perseverance, put this last word in your mind, and you will achieve it in the end. It is not just getting a degree, but cultivating yourself and motivating the next generations to fulfill their dreams. Being away from family is hard but often necessary.

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Ana

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Summary

Health-income inequalities are a global concern, yet people become ill and die because they do not have enough money to access the necessary health care that they need, and this situation is worse for people with disabilities. This thesis aims to better understand the role that income plays in promoting health in people living with Spinal Cord Injury (SCI), as an index case of disability. The research focused on three aspects, one, the estimation of the health income gap using years with the injury and a comorbidity index, two, the decomposition of different factors of this inequality with a special interest in the unmet healthcare needs, and three, their consequences in their social participation measured by the reasons of unemployment. The results show that even in more equal, and high-income countries with a universal health system, the living experience of people with SCI changes according to their income. On average, the gap between the richest and poorest income deciles goes from one to six years of living after the injury, and injuries due to work accidents showed the biggest gap. Regarding comorbidities, people in lower-income deciles are up to 40 times more likely to be ill than people in the richest-income deciles. The main difference in the years with the injury is explained by non-modifiable factors such as age. However, for the comorbidities, the unmet healthcare needs could explain 63% of the inequalities. These inequalities in health due to income also affect participation in the labor market. Health status represents the main barrier to entering the labor market, followed by a lack of sustainable employment opportunities and workplace accessibility issues. There are different realities for people according to their income before and after the injury, where the estimations and solutions for the 'average' individual do not target the needs of people in the extremes.

List of Abbreviations

ICF: International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health

ILO: International Labour Organization

InSCI: International Spinal Cord Injury survey

LHS-InSCI: Learning Health System for Spinal Cord Injury initiative

LIS: Luxemburg Income Study

PPP: Purchasing Power Parity

SCI: Spinal Cord Injury

SGDs: Sustainable Development Goals

WHO: World Health Organization

WID: World Inequality Database

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

Health equity is one of the most important challenges that health systems face [1, 2]. Providing appropriate care, in accordance with individual's needs, is a principle of social justice [3, 4, 5], and failing to do so has disproportionate effects on low-income groups [6, 7, 8]. Unfortunately, while there are numerous attempts and agreements to accomplish this general objective, achieving equity is challenging as its sources are diverse, many of which are not pertaining to the health system [9]. Literature has focused on the health-income gap in the general population [10, 11, 12], which inaccurately reflects the situation of vulnerable groups, like people with disabilities. Given the current population trends and increase in the incidence of non-communicable diseases, disability is central to population health. Thus, studying how inequality shapes the living situation of persons facing disabilities becomes crucial.

This doctoral dissertation aims to examine this gap and provide evidence of the health-income gap among one of the most vulnerable groups facing disability: persons with spinal cord injury (SCI) [13, 14]. This dissertation hypothesizes that income determines differences in health, where rich people tend to have a better health status (i.e., lower morbidity) and live longer compared to people in lower-income groups. Part of this inequity can be attributed to shortfalls in the healthcare system measured by unmet healthcare needs. In addition, these observed differences have important consequences for the activities and participation of people with disabilities, and the labor market reflects one of the most critical consequences. I performed an analysis across 22 countries with the goal of identifying areas for improvement describing the health-income gap, with a focus on unmet healthcare needs, unemployment levels, and the barriers to entering the market.

Though SCI has a low incidence worldwide, it is among the high-cost and high-needs groups [15]. SCI is an irreversible, chronic health condition that combines a high level of impairment with a series of comorbidities [15, 16]. Persons with SCI require frequent and specialized health care, and a responsive social support system to overcome the limitations faced when performing their daily activities [14, 15, 17]. Therefore, inequality can have more pervasive effects in these groups, as persons with SCI not only face limitations on their health but also on environmental and personal factors [18].

1.2 Definitions and key concepts

This work encompasses three core components: (1) using health-income inequalities as the general umbrella of this study; (2) focus on the SCI population; (3) using the International Spinal Cord Injury Survey (InSCI) as the main data source.

Health-income inequalities

Population health has improved almost everywhere: people live longer, and mortality is considerably lower [19]. However, this improvement has not been uniform, as people in lower income groups still have higher mortality and morbidity [20], with bigger gaps in developing countries. The factors that explain health disparities vary widely, including genetics, biology, behavior, and environment [21, 22, 23]. Most of these factors are strongly influenced by the socioeconomic status of a person, which explains why income plays a key role in understanding differences in population health globally [4, 11, 24]. The relationship between income and health has been long studied, and showing its causal effect is challenging due to a bidirectional effect: income determines health, and vice versa [6, 7, 8, 25, 26, 27, 28]. The relationship is shown to

be direct as more income, on average, translates into better health status (e.g., opportunities, longevity, health access) [28]. Nevertheless, the magnitude of this relationship is not always understood and has significant differences globally.

High-income countries generally report higher life expectancy and access to medicines and equipment than middle and low-income countries [4, 29], and within countries, poorer people face more unmet healthcare needs and die younger than richer people [4, 30]. For instance, at the country level, whereas the average life expectancy is above 80 years in countries like Japan and Sweden, it is only 72 years in Brazil, 63 years in India, and less than 50 years in some African nations. Regarding income distributions, in developing countries, children in the lowest income quintile are twice as likely to die before their fifth birthday compared to children in developed countries [1]. In contrast, children in the top income distribution have similar mortality rates to children in developed countries [31]. The issue is therefore not only poverty but also the distribution of resources that determine the distribution of opportunities. However, inequality also occurs within high-income countries. In the last few years, inequality has been rising steadily in most developed countries, where mortality and morbidity have shown marked differences across income groups [32]. Only in the United States between 2001 and 2014, those in the top 5% of the income distribution experienced an increase in life expectancy of about 3 years, while those in the poorest 5% experienced no increases [10].

A growing body of research indicates that income disparities have long-term effects on a population's health and social problems. Health indicators (e.g., mortality, morbidity, mental illness) and social problems (e.g., homicides, imprisonment, teenage births) tend to spike with rising inequality [23]. Health disparities are a global issue that must be addressed, especially those that result from a systematic, unequal allocation of resources among individuals, households, or per-capita income measures [5, 23]. At an individual level, health inequalities cause some people to have higher health risks than others or die sooner. At a societal level, the negative effects include crime, violence, poverty, urban blight, unemployment, and slower economic growth [4, 6, 25].

The gap in health outcomes between the top and bottom income categories exists in almost every country. It is more prominent in nations with higher levels of inequality and among more vulnerable groups, such as those with disabilities [29, 30, 31]. In most cases, studies have focused only on the average population, which hides the reality of people at the extremes of the income distribution, or those with higher health risks. To achieve equity, ensure the quality of life and improve health systems, it is important to pay special attention to the needs of the most vulnerable populations. To contribute to that, this thesis focuses on health-income inequalities among people with spinal cord injury as a demonstrative case of people facing higher levels of disability.

Spinal Cord Injury

Spinal cord injury (SCI) is a chronic health condition resulting from damage of the spinal cord or nerves at the end of the spinal canal. Those affected experience a medically complex and life-disrupting condition with a high dependence on the social and health system [15]. The incidence and prevalence of SCI are low compared to other health conditions; however, the consequences are often permanent, and the related costs are very high. SCI mostly results from traumatic incidents such as traffic accidents, work-related injuries, or leisure activities, but depending on the country some causes are attributed more to violence, falls, or non-traumatic incidents [15, 33]. In 2016, it was estimated that there were 0.93 million (0.78-1.16 million) new cases of SCI worldwide [34]; unfortunately, data on the prevalence of SCI are sparse. Currently, no

data source provides a reliable global or regional estimate of all-cause SCI prevalence. People with SCI confront a higher mortality risk and elevated comorbidities in comparison with the general population. The mortality rate can be two to five times higher, and this situation is exacerbated in low- and middle-income countries [15]. Secondary health conditions range from urinary problems to severe respiratory problems or chronic pain [16, 35]. For individuals with SCI, the mortality risk depends on the level and severity of the injury, but across countries, it depends on the health system response [18].

In general, the survival conditions after the injury have been improving, but with strong differences across countries. In developed countries, the life expectancy of people with SCI has increased since the 1950s, and the main cause of death is no longer secondary conditions [15]. However, in low-income countries, people still die immediately after the injury or due to preventable secondary health conditions, such as pressure sores or urologic complications [15]. Within countries, the needs of the SCI population differ too, while some individuals have access to rehabilitation and vocational services, in other situations, they are without access to a wheelchair [15, 17, 18, 36]. SCI can trigger physical, psychological, social, and economic shifts that affect almost all aspects of a person's life [37].

The direct and indirect costs of the injury depend on the health and social system support. For instance, in an estimation in Canada, during the first year of the injury for complete tetraplegia, the costs could reach 150.900 Canadian dollars, and for years 2-6 around 54.000 Canadian dollars each year [15]. If the health system does not cover those amounts, the out-of-pocket expenditures for the whole family increase [17]. Depending on how the health care system is structured, this can also influence many aspects aside from mortality and morbidity, such as employment, education, and social integration [18]. A lack of response from the system has been shown to diminish people's quality of life and increase their risk of poverty as a result of restricted participation and greater dependence on others [38].

Many countries have designed and implemented new efforts on the part of their health and social systems to improve the lived experiences of people with SCI. Nevertheless, notable gaps persist that, in many cases, are associated with their socioeconomic environment. Stigma and discrimination are common social problems and recurrent issues within this group [15]. Analyzing the relationship between income inequality and health for people with SCI is an opportunity to better understand and improve the social response to health services, of one of the most vulnerable groups of the population living with disabilities.

Data source: InSCI survey

The main data source of this thesis came from InSCI, which is part of the Learning Health System for Spinal Cord Injury initiative (LHS-InSCI). This initiative strengthens the collection of relevant and internationally comparable data on disability and supports research on disability and related services [13, 14]. InSCI is linked to the Model Disability Survey and uses the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) framework [14, 39], which makes it possible to compare across countries and comparisons to the general population. Because data on the incidence, prevalence, and mortality of people with SCI are inadequate and volatile [15, 34], InSCI provides a first step to generate comparable data on functioning, health maintained, and subjective well-being in SCI population [33, 39, 40]. InSCI seeks to capture the life experiences of people with SCI from different perspectives, not only personal but also environmental, through health systems, services, health care, and social and political aspects [33, 39, 40]. The data collected constitute very valuable input to identify problems and gaps in the structure and functioning of healthcare systems, which can help to improve the quality of life of people with disabilities [13, 15, 33].

The overall goal of the InSCI community survey is to identify the factors that explain the functioning

and well-being of people living with SCI. It encompasses aspects such as health, health-related, and other social and political systems, policies, services, and care provision [33, 39]. The data model includes 11 modules and 125 questions incorporating SCI health conditions with environmental factors and personal characteristics. Eligible persons are adults over 18 years of age with traumatic or non-traumatic SCI [33, 39, 40]. In the first edition of this survey, 22 countries from the six WHO regions participated, which represents 12,591 participants. Due to the scarce data on the SCI population in different countries, not all the countries involved used a random sample, 14/22 had a convenience sample. In addition, 4 countries had only the minimum number of participants (200), which is necessary for the comparison validity [33].

1.3 Study descriptions

This project is composed of three studies that analyze different outcomes in terms of income. The first study estimates disparities in two health outcomes: years with SCI and comorbidity index across income groups, between and within countries. The second study determines if variations in years with injury and the comorbidity index result from unmet healthcare needs, with poorer people facing greater hurdles. The third study investigates if income affects unemployment disparities among people with SCI.

Study 1. Health inequalities and income for people with spinal cord injury. A comparison between and within countries.

The first study estimates the health-income gap between and within countries. The research question was: How does income determine the years with the injury and the comorbidity index? To do that, first, it was important to build a comparable measure of income for each InSCI country, second, to build the health outcomes: comorbidity index and years with SCI, and finally, to adjust a model to build the health-income gap across countries.

For the first point, the comparable income measures the income deciles were chosen. The household income item was reported in the InSCI data in 10 levels. However, those levels were not standardized across the sample. Extra data sources were required to build the income deciles for each country and allocated to each participant by their purchasing power parity (PPP) in each country. The household income was standardized by the local currency, PPP in the year 2018, periodicity, and household size. The additional data come from the Luxemburg Income Study database (LIS) [41], the World Inequality Database (WID) [42], the European Commission database (Eurostat) [43], and single country-specific surveys [44, 45].

For the second point, to build the years with the injury it was considered the year of the injury and the year of the survey. For the comorbidity index, the secondary health conditions reported in the survey were used. The health conditions were weighted according to the mortality risk and the severity reported. The index was re-scaled 0-1 for interpretation purposes. For the last point, due to the heterogeneity of the sample hierarchical models were used to capture the variability between countries with random effects by country (i.e., intercept) and individual income (i.e., slope). Individual regressions were assessed to analyze the variability within countries. The results were plotted by country and cause of injury for a better representation of the gaps.

Study 2. Unmet healthcare needs and health inequalities in people with spinal cord injury. A direct regression inequality decomposition.

Once the gap was estimated, the second study deconstructed health-income inequality focusing on the role of the health system through unmet healthcare needs. The hypothesis of this study was that the unmet healthcare needs explain a great part of the health gap between income groups, and the research question was: To what extent do the unmet healthcare needs explain the health-income inequalities in the years with SCI and the comorbidity index?

First, the Gini index was used to show the concentration of each health outcome in each country. To include the income variable in the analysis, in a second step the Erreygers concentration index was estimated considering the health outcome and the income distribution in each country. Finally, a direct regression approach was used to analyze the importance of unmet healthcare needs in health outcomes. The analysis was done by country and by health outcome.

Study 3. Disability, unemployment, and inequality. A cross-country comparison of the situation of persons living with spinal cord injury.

The last study extended the analysis to the consequences of income inequality in the exclusion of participants from the labor market. The objective was to examine the reasons for unemployment of people with SCI as they relate to income distribution. The hypothesis was that the reasons for exclusion from the labor market differ depending on income level.

To that end, first, it was important to define the study population in terms of working age and unemployment. Second, through logistic regression, the probability to be unemployed was estimated for the whole sample and by each reason reported. Finally, to better understand the unemployment reasons by country and the gap between income groups a heat map was used as a comparison with the general population.

1.4 Summary and main results

The objective of this thesis was to generate evidence about the role of income in the health disparities of people with SCI across countries. The first study provided the health-income gap measured by country and the cause of the injury. The second study estimated which part of the inequality was explained by the unmet healthcare needs. Finally, the third study focused on the consequences of the inequalities measured by the reasons for unemployment.

Study 1. Health inequalities and income for people with spinal cord injury. A comparison between and within countries.

The first study estimated the health-income gap between the richest and poorest income groups in two health outcomes: years with SCI and comorbidity index. The results show that people in the highest income deciles live more years after the injury and with fewer comorbidities than people in the lowest income groups in the InSCI countries. Due to the self-selection of the data in the income variable, the final results of this paper included only 51% of the original data (6,445 participants). Poland, Germany, France, Switzerland, Spain, Greece, Romania, South Korea, China, and Australia were involved in the

analysis. For these countries, the health gap between the richest and the poorest income groups ranges from 1 to 6 years in the health outcome years with SCI, and up to forty times more comorbidities.

The results vary considerably by country, cause of the injury, and type of income (personal vs. national income). For the first outcome, years with SCI, while the gap in Greece was around seven years (6.7 years), in China and South Korea an indirect relationship was shown. In these countries, the gap was favorable for low-income groups, with 1.5 and 3.25 years, respectively. In the comorbidity index, only France showed a slight pro-poor gap (0.38 vs 0.40). In terms of income, in the first outcome, the national income is predicted better by years with SCI, while comorbidities matter more than personal income. These inequalities are also seen in relation to the cause of the injury. For the years with SCI, work-related accidents showed the steepest gap (two years), followed by injuries caused by traffic, sports, and leisure activities with less than one year. For the comorbidity index, injuries caused by traffic accidents, falls, sports, and leisure activities showed a gap higher than 15%, while the gap due to work accidents and violence was around 8%.

Study 2. Unmet healthcare needs and health inequalities in people with spinal cord injury. A direct regression inequality decomposition.

The second study analyzed the importance of unmet healthcare needs as a modifiable aspect to explain health disparities due to income. The analysis included as well other factors both modifiable and non-modifiable to have a better description of the inequalities. This study included information on the 22 countries in the InSCI survey, with complete information on the health outcomes and income variables (11,529 participants). The results showed an unequal distribution of health outcomes in the InSCI countries, where unmet healthcare needs contributed to the inequalities, especially to the comorbidity index outcome.

For the years with SCI, Morocco showed the highest unequal situation. The Gini index was 0.45, followed closely by the USA and the Netherlands (0.43). A less unequal situation was shown in China with an index of 0.3. When the concentration index was calculated considering the income, the Erreygers concentration index was significant in 9 of 20 countries: China, Switzerland, Poland, Germany, Malaysia, Lithuania, Japan, Greece, and South Africa. Meaning that the health outcome: of years with the injury is higher concentrated in high-income groups. Only China showed a pro-poor situation, where people in fewer income groups are living more than those in higher income groups.

For the comorbidities index, the concentration index was smaller than for the first outcome, but still, an unequal distribution was observed. The lowest Gini index was in Brazil with 0.09, and the highest value was in South Korea with 0.27. When income was included in the concentration index, 10 countries showed a significant Erreygers concentration index. While most countries showed a pro-rich inequality situation, China, Italy, and Japan showed a slightly pro-poor situation (i.e., fewer comorbidities in the poorest income groups). The results showed that age and unmet healthcare needs are the factors with higher importance to explain health inequalities. While age, a non-modifiable factor, in some countries accounted for more than 60% of the difference in concentration of health among income groups, unmet healthcare needs were the main factor affecting for the comorbidity index. In 14 of 22 countries, the weight of unmet healthcare needs was greater than 20%.

Study 3. Disability, unemployment, and inequality. A cross-country comparison of the situation of persons living with spinal cord injury.

The third study in this thesis reflects the inequality in unemployment conditions of people with SCI. The analysis focused on the probability to be out of the labor market and the reasons behind this reality by country. This paper included 20 of the 22 countries due to it was not possible to get the income decile for Malaysia and Indonesia. In addition, only people of working age and active in the labor market (employed or unemployed) were considered. The data set included 5,411 participants.

In general, unemployment rates for people with disabilities are higher than those for the general population. In this sample, the unemployment rate is, on average, around 40% for people with SCI in the InSCI countries analyzed. The main reason behind these higher values is due to the health condition of the participants; however, these values vary markedly by income group. The probability to be unemployed due to health status is 42% in the poorest income decile, while in the wealthiest is only 11%. The second reason is the inability to find a suitable job; the probability is 22% for the first income decile (decile 1) and 5% for the last income decile (decile 10).

These inequalities vary by country and income level. In most countries, the health of the participants is the main reason for unemployment; however, there are other relevant reasons, such as lack of information, transportation, accessibility, and fear to lose disability benefits. The highest unemployment gap between income groups was in South Africa at 65 percentage points (84% vs. 19%). Morocco, China, and South Korea showed substantial inequality between the top and the bottom income groups, with more than 50 percentage points. The smallest gaps were in Norway, Switzerland, Australia, and Japan, with less than 8 percentage points. Another surprising result was that in South Africa, Spain, Poland, and Switzerland, people in the top income deciles showed lower unemployment rates than the general population.

1.5 General discussion and interpretation of the results

The country's income and personal income explain the greatest number of health disparities in people with spinal cord injury, which have consequences not only on their health but also on social interactions with the community. The health inequalities due to income are present before the injury, as the different risks and exposure to the causes of the injury, and after the injury could just increase if people do not receive the appropriate health and social support.

This thesis is a descriptive analysis of the living experiences of people with SCI across countries and how income determines them. The three studies show the direct influence of personal and national income on health from different points of view the extent of the health-income gap between countries, the measure of inequalities due to unmet healthcare needs, and the reasons for unemployment in relation to income distribution across and within countries. These results are in line with previous knowledge about the social determinants of health, which has mostly been analyzed for the general population and at the national level.

Assessing the health-income gap in the first study affirmed the disparate realities across countries and the role of income before and after the injury. Income at both national and personal levels determines survival rates and life experiences after the injury. Not only does it matter which part of the spine is injured, but one's country and the cause of the injury also matter. In more equitable countries, people's injuries are likely to be the result of falls, when they are older or sports at younger ages, while in more inequitable

countries, they are often caused by work accidents and violence. These reflect existing inequalities due to the socioeconomic conditions of the person and the country.

In countries with comprehensive healthcare systems that include rehabilitation, people are able to continue with a productive life for more than 20 years after an SCI and overcome the challenges more effectively. In low- and middle-income countries, the survival rate is lower; a clear indication of this is the low number of tetraplegics in these samples. When injured people survive, they become the responsibility of the whole family and/or society. Having a clearer picture of the health-income gap and the distinctions between countries and causes of injury is an important tool for navigating the causes and consequences of these inequalities.

The second study shows that the distribution of health outcomes is unequally distributed according to individual income levels. While there are non-modifiable factors such as age that influence health variability, other factors such as unmet healthcare needs play an important role in the discussion of inequalities. Unmet healthcare needs are mainly due to health costs [36], and this factor can be modifiable by the intervention of the health and social system. The pro-poor situation that some countries show further accentuates inequalities after injury.

In the last paper, the consequences of these inequalities are reflected in their labor participation. The unemployment rates for people with SCI are higher in comparison with the general population and these ones are different by income level. The probability to be unemployed is higher for people in low-income groups than for people in higher-income groups. People do not work because of their health condition, and they are sicker because of the high unmet healthcare needs. In general, the income reflects the unequal exposition, survival rates, medical provision, and quality of life across countries. If a person receives the appropriate support, the probability to reintegrate into society with a good health status is higher. In addition, if their personal income is higher, people can afford additional support as health caregivers or assistive devices even in another country, allowing them higher participation in society. However, there is an additional exclusion due to financial constraints. People do not access the health service they need because they cannot pay for them, affecting their health and their chances of working.

1.6 Strengths and limitations

The main strength of the present project lies in the evidence collected, showing different factors that determine the living experiences of people with SCI in terms of income and the country where they live. This thesis contributes directly to the sustainable development goals (SGD) 3 and 10 [2], which aim to reduce inequalities and guarantee appropriate health and wellness. It focused on a vulnerable group of the population, showing a complete history line from the measure of the health-income gap, the factors of inequality, and their consequences. In addition, it provides an analysis at the country level and within the country, which facilitates the analysis of the disparate realities of people with similar health conditions but in different environments.

Nevertheless, some limitations in the present thesis should be acknowledged. First, the InSCI survey is self-reported data that does not include representative SCI populations in all countries. Convenience sampling can generate bias in some countries, and there was not enough data for more desegregation of the results. Second, it was not possible to build the whole income gradient, just a health gap between the bottom and top income groups. Some income groups could be over or underrepresented, and there was no other data source to validate it. Finally, it is a descriptive analysis, in which this thesis does not provide

a causal analysis of the variables used.

1.7 Policy implications

The results of this thesis have several implications for policy at the international and national levels. People have different health risks and not everyone needs the same services, it is important to track subgroups of the population focused on the most vulnerable ones between and within countries. The studies for the general population do not reflect the situation of the most vulnerable ones, for that reason first, it is important to identify the at-risk populations, the excluded groups with limited or no access to health and social support. Second, it is needed to understand the reasons for these risks, why vulnerable people face lack access to health services in terms of health conditions, economic, social, and cultural aspects, and how to provide them with financial protection. Third, it is important to prioritize the areas for intervention, which will be related to the country's and the population's needs. Finally, to better support policy making, is required good data and made available. With appropriate data, equity indicators can be built, tracked, and compared with other countries. This will provide a reference level to learn and identify target areas. Tracking only the average or the national levels provides just a global picture of the countries but overlooks other realities within the countries and across them. Healthy people and a healthy environment do not come only from the health system, the systematic causes of inequality need to be targeted from a complete and interactive framework, including the social system. Future studies need to focus on the situation within countries to show what to do, and how to do it.

The contributions of this project are directly related to vertical equity. It focuses on a group of the population with different needs and more barriers to face than the general population, and the comparison across countries and income groups. The results show that income needs to be included in the health inequalities analysis, understood as one of the main causes of health disparities. The conditions of people with SCI are different from the general population, there is a need to focus on and track the most vulnerable ones between and within countries. Finally, the country comparison allows us to better understand the areas to improve and focus on policymaking in the different realities

1.8 Conclusion

Social determinants, such as income and the country where people live, predict the greatest number of health disparities, which differ in vulnerable groups. People with disabilities are vastly different from the general population. The problem is not only the direct consequences of their injury; it is also a collection of problems, such as precarious working conditions and exclusion from the social system, among others, before and after the injury. There is an evident gap in health due to income, and it has consequences that involve health status, activities, and participation in society. The main reason for unemployment is health, and unmet healthcare needs are an important component of this inequality. To achieve equity, healthcare services alone cannot reduce vulnerabilities. Integrated policies are needed to target populations with higher health risks and the causes behind those vulnerabilities. Failure to identify and target them generates still more systemic inequalities.

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Chapter 2

Health inequalities and income for people with spinal cord injury. A comparison between and within countries.

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Chapter 3

Unmet healthcare needs and health inequalities in people with spinal cord injury. A direct regression inequality decomposition.

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Chapter 4

Disability, Unemployment, and Inequality A cross country comparison of the situation for persons with spinal cord injury.

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